

Introduction

Good Governance is the dream of every society, Nigeria inclusive. Nigeria is a great nation, blessed and endowed with both human and natural resources that when properly managed, would enhance good governance, and will in turn attract both local and foreign investors that would build her economy. Administration and management plays a very vital role in enhancing good governance. It is one thing to be blessed with human and natural resources, it is another thing to management them in order to achieve the expected result, as in every administration, there are set goals, manifestos, the expectations from the general public and citizens, which must be met.

Wikipedia defines good governance as:

Good governance is the process of necessarily how public institutions conduct public affairs and manage public resources and guarantee the realization of human rights in a manner essentially free of abuse and corruption and with due regards for the rule of law

Administration and management are as old as man. According to biblical concept or precept, it is a fact that man was to manage a garden that was made and given to him as his home, a place of his abode. He was to manage this home and to keep to instructions. I will say here that the origin of administration and management is God's agenda right from the beginning of creation. In the book of Genesis 2:15: "And the Lord God took man and put him into the Garden of Eden to dress it and to keep it." Adam, the first man was just as a steward in the garden, he was placed over to keep it in order. According to Oxford language dictionary, administration is the process or activity of running a business, or an organization. The day to day administration of a company, organization or nation. In every administration, there are policies on how the affairs are to be runned or operated. God gave Adam specific instructions on what is to be done and what is not to be done as a policy, man chose to do other wise and we lost his estate and was chased out, guards placed on the all the four enterances to prevent him from gaining future access into it. Inability to hold on or stick to the laid down policy or produce, it leads to mismanagement. In as much as administration and management started with the early man. Mismanagement and default also occurred during his time. Therefore, the author intends to assess and evaluate good governance in Nigeria and come up with seven fundamental managerial components that are essential to good governance.

The researcher applied the qualitative method to obtain his data; in the process of carrying out this research, both primary and secondary sources were employed. The primary source of obtaining data was mainly through personal observations of happenings, while the secondary source of data was by consulting and exploring other materials and research work of other authors through the online process.

Definition of Terms

Administration

Administration is the day to day operation of activities within a given organization, business or nation. It is the management of public affairs. Oxford language Dictionary defines administration as "The process or activity of running a business, organization etc. or the management of public affairs, government. Merriam Webster Dictionary looks at it as a "performance of executive duties or the act or process of administering something." Administration is also seen as a group constituting the political executive in a presidential government. Administration is an act or process of carrying out functions or activities in a given organization, administration, or business. Administration serves as a medium in which an organization can be run, functioned, operated. The Holy Bible said in I Corinthians 12:5 that, "And there are differences of administration, but the same Lord." Administration must be anchored on God's principles. Apostle Paul, in the book of II Corinthians 9:12, cited the functions of a particular administration, which was not just meeting the needs of the

saints, but abundant also by many thanksgiving unto God who is the source of all. The administration was not limited to their function, but as well recognizes the one who gives the enablement and the supplies. According to the Bible, administration is service unto the people and unto God.

Management

Management is to manage something. According to Mariam Webster Dictionary, to manage is, to handle or direct with a degree of skill such as, (a) to exercise, executive administrative, and supervisory direction of (b) To treat with care (c) To make and keep. Management is ‘the act or art of managing: the conducting or supervising of something such as business, judicious use or means to accomplish an end (5) The collective body of those who manage or direct an enterprise. Management is to see that things are properly done. It is a process engaged upon, with deliberate and concerted effort to ensure proper arrangement and accomplishment of set goals.

Management can also be seen as getting things done through people as things cannot be done on their own except someone somewhere act or perform certain function. When things are left to be done on then own, them nothing will be done, and no tangible or meaningful result will be attained. Management is to ensure that things that are to be done are properly done.

Furthermore, management has to do with coordinating monitoring and enforcing proper action into performance of duties so as to attain and achieve set goals (strategic coordination) directing and controlling affairs within an organization or nation. Peter Drucker (2018), known as the father of management based on his meaningful contributions to management theory and practice, said that management requires specialized knowledge and skills. ‘Management’s goal is to make human abilities productive and human weaknesses irrelevant? Management requires skillful knowledgeable and professional application of all available resources at disposal to achieve expected and set goals.

Good Governance

This is a state where the administration and management resources promote peaceful coexistence and ... development of a given society. Good governance can never be enhanced or achieved without good and effective administration and management of both human & material resources. Good governance is the ability of rulers or leadership of a given organization or nation to put things right especially where the role of law, judicious and even distribution of resources, as well as right implementation of policies. According to Wikipedia ‘Good Governance is the process measuring how public institutions conduct public affairs and manage public resources and guarantee the realization of human rights in a manner essentially free of abuse and corruption and with due regards for the role of law.’ In good governance, there is decentralization of power, positions and appointments dispersed and distributed among the ethnic groups, tribes and gender. Good governance should be void of communal crisis, violence, lawlessness, abuse of power or privileges, corruption/bribery, rioting, threat to life, religious intolerance, hanachy, inhumanity to man, or any other social vices that will lead to disturbance or obstruction of peace and the development of society.

Seven Fundamental Managerial Components

The seven fundamental managerial components (Agencies) that are essential to good governance are listed as follows:

- 1) Security and the law enforcement agencies.
- 2) Agency of socialization.
- 3) Infrastructure and social amenities
- 4) Human/personnel resources’
- 5) Natural/material resources
- 6) Financial resources
- 7) International Relations

Security: Security outfits are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring safety of lives and properties. Nigeria is blessed with top most security and law enforcement agencies that are to collaborate and collectively combat crime. Some of their functions covers counter terrorism, drugs/human trafficking money laundering and corruption related issues. Oxford language dictionary defines security as “free from danger or threat.” This is very essential and should be the top most priority of every governance. In his view, Raymond Temituro (2024) states that, “law enforcement agencies in Nigeria are all established to enforce the law without bias, but each agency has a different focus.” With the Nigerian Immigration Service in charge of our borders to prevent illegal entry into the country. Nigerian Custom Service with the primary focus on imported goods into the country and to root out smugglers and traffickers who engage in illicit act such as drugs. The body determines what comes in and out of the country. This will determine the safety of lives and properties. If there is safety in the country, good governance commences.

What is more, the independence corrupt practices commission (ICPC) alongside Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) are to fight and checkmate fraudulence activities, corruption, money laundering. They have to enforce the law by recovering stolen funds while the culprits face their charges. The Nigerian Police Force and, their counterpart, Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDS) are to ensure that lives and properties are secured. If all these powerful and well-funded Agencies will be given free hands to operate, it will go along way to boast good governance in Nigeria. The NIA, DSS that are to provide intelligence report to the government and as well to fight counter terrorism. Nigeria is capable of providing good governance with the aid of her security Agencies

Agencies of Socialization: Socialization has three primary goals: (1) Teaching impulse control and developing a conscience; (2) Preparing people to perform certain social roles; and (3) Cultivating shared resources of meaning and value. Among the numerous agencies of socialization in Nigeria, two will be picked for discussion. These are educational institutions (schools) and the mass media. The educational institutions are places where the work force expertise, professional skills, knowledge, confidence, and competence are being obtained. A society can never be better without her educational institutions. “Schools are directly responsible for making people worthwhile in their respective societies.” Education has the ability to influence our behaviour, grows and shape the mindset and prepare an individual to handle situations in a professional way. Educational institution, as an agent of socialization, is expected to manufacture responsible citizens. The lawyers, doctors, nurses, engineers, mechanical, politicians, etc. are all products of our Educational Institutions, the Schools. So our educational institutions should be given adequate attention as they form the basis for good morals, skills, expertise, professionalism, effective service delivery and attainment of good governance.

On the other hand, the mass media is another agency that is of utmost importance when it comes to good governance. The mass media transmit, disseminate information to the general public through various means such as radio, magazines, newspapers, emails, internet, and the television. Dictionary.com defines mass media as ‘the means of communication to reach large number of people in a short time such as television, newspapers, magazines and radio. In a situation where the mass media with the sole responsibility of disseminating information to the general people begin to hoard information, denying the citizens of the rightful happenings in the society because those in authority are sheeding their evil acts and practices, this is bad governance. The citizens have the right to know what happens in the community where they reside. Vital and sensitive information is not to be hoarded but disseminated for public consumption. The public must be sensitized and well informed so the mass media must be free from external influence by the authoritative.

Infrastructure: Infrastructure according to Oxford language Dictionary is “the basic, physical and organizational structures and facilities (eg) buildings roads, power supplies) needed for the operation of a society or enterprise.” Furthermore, Investopedia defines it as “the basic, physical systems of a business, region or nation and often involves the production of public goods or production processes.” Examples of infrastructure include transportation systems, communication networks, sewage, water and schools. Transportation system such as rail for easy access and mobility within the city, pipeborne water for good drinking water for the citizens, good and modern structures and facilities in our educational sector and good communication system both for the security agencies and the mass media will form good governance infrastructure which serves or forms our national and collective assets should be properly funded and maintained and protected. Digital Lib.washington Proposed four key analytic elements of sustainability theory for civil infrastructure as (1) Environmental infrastructure (2) Technical Infrastructure (3) Economic Infrastructure (4) Social Infrastructure.

Human/Personnel Resources: Human or Personnel resources is referred to as the work force of an organization, establishment or a nation. These are people who carry out specific functions in an organization in order to attain or achieve set or common goals. Without personnels, work can never be done. Human/Personnel Resources as defined by Oxford Language Dictionary, “The personnel of a business or organization, regarded as a significant asset in terms of skills and abilities.” According to Wikipedia, “Human Resources is the set of people who made up the workforce of an organization, business sector, industry or economy. A narrower concept is human capital, the knowledge and skills which the individual command. Similar terms include manpower, labour power or personnel.” If work must be done, how the work could be done, with desired result achieved, then personnels have to be properly managed. It requires regular trainings, advance courses, supervision, motivation and inspiration on the personnels in order for them to put in their best to duty. Disciplinary action should also be applied or enforced when or where necessary to serve as a deterrent to those who would want to go against the laid down rules and regulations or code of conduct, as would be applied in the organization.

If the human or personnel resources would be properly managed then our industries, institutions, agencies, will thrive.

Natural/Material Resources: These are resources that are found naturally on the earth without human efforts. There are God-given resources to be exploited extracted, processed and use by man. Britannica defines natural resources as any biological mineral or aesthetic asset afforded by nature without human intervention that can be used for some form benefits, whether material (economic) or immaterial. Britannica further cited some examples natural resources such as, (forest, surface water and ground water and fertile lands or the soil and minerals within them, rather than the crops that grow on them, as well as energy such as petroleum, natural gas, and heated water (that is geothermal energy) contained within layers or rock. Nigeria is indeed endowed with these natural resources such as crude oil, forest, gold granites metals coal, soil, to mention a few. If this endowment would be properly managed, will promote the economic growth of the nation (Wikipedia). Natural resources are resources that are drawn from nature and used with few modifications. Nigeria is rich with natural resources so can never be referred to as a poor or under develop nation but to be seen among the top developed nations in the world.

Financial Resources: Financial resources as defined by University of New York: “Financial resources are the funds and assets that finance an organization’s activities and investment.” Two types of financial resources are mentioned which are internal financial resources, which comes from within the businesses or organization in form of profit generated while the external financial resources are mainly funds that come from outside the business or organization which includes loans and credits from external sources such as banks. Financial resources stands as a fundamental pillar in sustaining stability and growth. “Financial resources represents the tangible and intangible assets available to an

individual, organization or government to meet financial needs” (Designmatch). Financial resources are the upkeep of an individual, business, organization, or a nation. It is the strength in which development, progress, success, attainment of set goals can be attained or achieved. The funds of Nigerian that comes from production, refining revenue collection and tax is meant for development, meeting the needs of the sustainable citizens and as a pride of every nation.

International Resources: This is a relationship that exist between one nation with another in terms of security, trade and investment. San Fransisco State University, Department of international relation, said, “International relations is concerned with relations across boundaries of nation-states. It addresses international policies, economy, global governance, intercultural relations, national and ethnic identities foreign policy analysis, development studies, environment, international security, diplomacy, terrorism, media social movements and many more. International Relations should not just be based on theory but in practical terms where nation, states relates well. All these areas mentioned above according to San Francisco University, should be properly managed so as to be in good relations with other nation – states for economy growth and development, peaceful coexistence and sharing of ideas in politics, religion, education, military, security and & many more relationship among nations.

Findings

- ❖ Despite the fact that Nigeria has quite a number of security outfit security of lives and properties is still a major problem and concern.
- ❖ Kidnapping, terrorism, communal crises among other social vices is still prevalence in the country on the increase.
- ❖ Nigeria still have in flock of immigrants because our borders are not properly secured Mr. David parradang, The controller General of NIS disclosed in the cable news that Nigeria has over 1,400 illegal border routes Taiwo George April 24, 2014 with only 84 approved land control posts. As of now, there should be more.
- ❖ Despite the huge natural and material resources deposited in Nigeria, Nigeria is still looking up to other foreign nations for assistance and loans Nigeria is among the poorest and undeveloped nations.
- ❖ The nation’s funds is still being embezzled, cyphoned and converted into private accounts for personal use. Looters, fraudsters, corrupters, enbezzlers all over. The constituencies are left unattended to. Funds meant for the development of these constituencies is being pocketed and chyphoned.
- ❖ Our educational institutions that are supposed to be taken as topmost priority are being neglected, and ignored. Series of strikes have become a common thing in Nigeria where negotiations between the government and ASSU will never held tangible result as government does not keep to their promises nor are ready or willing to go by the agreed terms.
- ❖ Marginalization is another bitter experience. The qualified competent and resourceful are not given the privilege to rule, rather money is being used to seek for power and position. Certain sets of tribes or individuals are not allowed into certain sensitive positions. This is barbaric.
- ❖ Justice being perverted, the right of the masses being denied the rule of law does not applied to those in authority as they are above the law.
- ❖ The infrastructure, social amenities such as water, power, and good roads are not taken care of. Our roads have become dead traps citizens now depend on generators as source of light, bottle or pure water for drinking.

Recommendations

- There is need to buff up security agencies. Security Agencies have to buff up security in the country to ensure that the issue of insecurity will be in the minimal not on the increase on incontrollable.
- The Judiciary should be independent to interpret the law and defend the Nigerian constitution. Grant fair hearing to all citizens and make sure that perpetrators of crime should be made to face the law.
- Those in charge of Nigerian borders are to step up to their responsibilities and limit or reduce the influx of immigrants into the country by deploying every means necessary.
- Nigerians should ensure that the right, competent and credible candidates be appointed, nominated or elected into leadership positions. The trusted and reliable people of integrity and accountability. Those that are sound and healthy. Nigerian should avoid selling or mortgaging their future for pee-nuts.
- The government should try and build good transportation network system for easy mobility and movement of people and goods, create enabling learning environment in all our institutions of learning. Give the mass media free hands of operation by disseminating right information at the right time.
- Funds realized from production workforce, revenue and tax collection should be judiciously used in the right direction by providing the necessary needs of the citizens.
- Agencies that are meant to fight corruption, fraud and financial related crimes should also rise up to their responsibilities and secure the nation's economy.
- International relations should be properly built with other nations for good relations that will build trust of investment in the country.

Conclusion

Good Governance is possible in Nigeria as it has what it takes to be among the best and developed nations of the world. This can be achieved through proper management of all available resources, effective administration and implementation of policies, and adherence to the constitution that guide the nation. In the area of security, Nigeria is capable. Related to natural and material resources, Nigeria has it all. In terms of personnel, Nigeria has the best hands. So, why shouldn't Nigeria attain good governance? Nigeria, the giant and pride of Africa, can as well be the giant of the world, if the right things can be done. And this can only be made possible through effective administration and management with the help of God.

About The Author

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Online Resources

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